

Mathematics for and from STEM: Conceptualising successful mathematics integration in STEM education

Michelle Fitzpatrick

Mary Immaculate College, Limerick

The pace of STEM policy and curricular change in Ireland gives impetus to exploring more integrated approaches to STEM education. In turn, it challenges traditional, disciplinary approaches to teacher education, forcing us to reimagine how we prepare our future teachers for integrated STEM. This paper presents an effort to support 27 pre-service primary teachers in unearthing productive mathematical learning opportunities within integrated STEM tasks. It reports on pre-service teachers' experiences across two modules over two years. We outline the challenges experienced by both the pre-service teachers and teacher educators, before suggesting and trialling a framework for meaningful mathematics integration in STEM tasks. Preliminary findings suggest that the framework has potential to capitalise on mathematical opportunities across a STEM inquiry cycle. This study has implications for mathematics education in initial teacher education, where recent developments demand a balance of both disciplinary and interdisciplinary approaches.

Keywords: Mathematics education, integrated STEM, primary pre-service teachers

Introduction

There has been a recognised need for more integrated approaches to STEM (Honey et al., 2014). Although this has been met with enthusiasm from teachers (Hourigan et al., 2022), challenges abound which impede effective implementation (Margot & Kettler, 2019). One challenge is in maintaining a balance between the disciplines, with the underrepresentation of mathematics being particularly evident (English, 2016; Maass et al., 2019). Despite being generally accepted as the underpinning discipline in STEM, mathematics is often reduced to a service role in STEM tasks with little opportunity for genuine mathematical learning (Tytler et al., 2019; Forde et al., 2023). Meanwhile, teachers have reportedly struggled to identify opportunities for authentic mathematics teaching and learning within STEM tasks (Tytler et al., 2019). In this paper, we demonstrate how primary pre-service teachers (PSTs) can be supported in maintaining the spotlight on mathematics in integrated STEM tasks, by examining the role of mathematics teaching and learning for STEM and mathematics teaching and learning from STEM.

Background and study context

STEM education continues to attract global attention. The Irish policy landscape is no exception. Ambitious goals were set by the *STEM Education Policy Statement 2017-2026* (DES, 2017) mapping out a vision for STEM education engagement across the sectors. STEM policy is now aligning with curricular change at primary level. While mathematics and science are currently treated as isolated subjects, the new *Primary Curriculum Framework* (NCCA, 2023) sees the introduction of STEM education as one of five new broad curriculum areas. A STEM education development group has also recently been assembled, to prepare for the design of a national primary STEM curriculum.

Traditional teacher education programmes have focused on developing skills and knowledge in the individual disciplines. Pre-service teachers, therefore, are rarely provided with opportunities to develop pedagogical approaches to integrated STEM. Given the increased emphasis on interdisciplinary approaches, practices need to be reimagined, as teachers feel unprepared to teach in integrated ways (Shernoff et al., 2017).

Methodology

Participants were 27 primary pre-service teachers undertaking a mathematics specialism course as part of their Bachelor of Education programme. As part of a larger study investigating PSTs' evolving understanding of integrated STEM education, this paper follows the PSTs across two elective modules and reports on their experiences of integrating meaningful and authentic mathematics in STEM tasks. In the second semester of their third year (*Phase 1*), PSTs worked with three teacher educators across a 12-week integrated STEM intervention. As part of this module, PSTs designed and taught five STEM tasks to a fifth class in a partner school. PSTs and teacher educators then reflected on field practice, with a particular focus on the positioning of mathematics within each lesson. In the second semester of their fourth year (*Phase 2*), the same PSTs returned to the role of mathematics within STEM. Over five weeks, PSTs reconsidered the positioning of mathematics in STEM task design. They examined the role of mathematics during a STEM inquiry cycle, seeking out opportunities for rich mathematical teaching and learning at each stage of the process.

Data collection methods include pre-post intervention surveys, field notes, reflective journal entries, video recordings of lessons, post-teaching focus groups (*Phase 1*) and group-designed STEM tasks and interviews (*Phase 2*). Data from *Phase 1* were analysed using a grounded theory approach. Codes were generated and a constant comparison method was used to examine the data within and across each participant's data corpus. Data collected in *Phase 2* were deductively analysed based on the findings from *Phase 1*. Ethical approval was granted by the institution's research ethics committee and all considerations were adhered to.

Findings and conclusions

Phase 1

The pre-intervention data reflects high levels of confidence amongst the PSTs in their ability to teach mathematics. Participants attributed this confidence to success and enjoyment in their mathematics education modules, as well as in their professional school placement. Following the integrated STEM education intervention, however, there was concern amongst the PSTs relating to how mathematics could be meaningfully integrated in STEM. This was particularly evident following field practice. While video analysis and post-teaching focus group discussions suggest that the tasks were successful in promoting some STEM learning (notably science, engineering and 21st century skills), there was no evidence of planned, age-appropriate mathematical teaching and learning across the five lessons. Furthermore, the PSTs initially viewed the unambitious and incidental mathematical activities that were present (such as lower-order computation and measurement) as authentic mathematics integration and had significant difficulty in recognising opportunities to explore rich mathematical content and promote mathematical thinking.

We have detailed elsewhere (Fitzpatrick, et al., 2023) some possible reasons for the lack of mathematical learning in these STEM tasks. Firstly, by prioritising engineering practices (the initial source of concerns for PSTs), we, as teacher educators, underestimated the need to maintain the spotlight on mathematics in STEM and made assumptions about the ease with which PSTs would apply their experiences in mathematics education to more integrated approaches. Secondly, no curriculum-based learning outcomes were identified that would focus on the mathematical skills and understanding to be developed. Finally, the task parameters did not stimulate mathematical thinking or reasoning. Given the difficulties in realising productive mathematics within integrated STEM tasks, we suggest that conscious decisions must be made about *where* and *when* we position mathematics and STEM in our teaching. We argue that reflecting on mathematics learning opportunities before, during and after STEM tasks in the planning process, would support PSTs in recognising rich opportunities for mathematics in STEM inquiry cycles, allowing discrete disciplinary learning to inform meaningful integrated work and vice versa. In turn, we offer the terms **mathematics learning for STEM** and **mathematics learning from STEM** (Fitzpatrick, et al., 2023).

Mathematics learning for STEM. Specific disciplinary knowledge and skills, developed in preceding discrete mathematics lessons, to be utilised and developed in new ways during the STEM task.

Mathematics learning from STEM. New mathematical knowledge and skills developed during the STEM task. Furthermore, it may also refer to new mathematical concepts that the STEM task presents, whereby the STEM tasks act as both a rich context and a springboard for future mathematical inquiries.

Phase 2

Phase 2 of this study utilises the findings from Phase 1 as a framework for designing a mathematics-focused integrated STEM task. Attention was focused on the potential for spotlighting the ‘M’ in integrated STEM, by: ensuring tasks contain reference to relevant *explicit mathematics disciplinary content*; identifying *curriculum-based mathematics learning objectives*; setting *task criteria and parameters* that stimulate mathematical reasoning; and providing *mathematical materials* that promote mathematical thinking. PSTs were also guided to consider meaningful opportunities for discrete mathematical learning *for* and *from* STEM. Emerging findings suggest that the PSTs successfully used the framework to uncover potential for rich mathematical learning at different stages of the inquiry cycle. In their groups (5-6 PSTs), pre-service teachers were required to design integrated STEM tasks (based on *the honeybee*) that positioned mathematics as the central discipline. The groups each identified appropriate mathematical concepts and skills to be developed while remaining attentive to the characteristics of an integrated STEM lesson. Two lessons focused on the honeycomb structure, exploring geometry (shape and tessellation) and measures (capacity and volume). A third lesson also explored volume, this time presenting a Fermi problem to estimate the number of bees that would fit in a given area. The fourth lesson was centred around statistics, using data sets and maps to determine the best location for bee populations. The final lesson set children the task of designing a school ‘pollinator garden’, offering a series of dimension parameters to investigate measurement. While aspects of the tasks needed further

development, there was a striking difference in terms of mathematical engagement, age-appropriate content, as well as an increase in mathematical cognitive demand, compared to earlier tasks designed. These preliminary findings, while limited, suggest that this framework has potential to support PSTs in foregrounding mathematics in integrated STEM tasks, and warrants further investigation. Data collection is ongoing.

References

- Department of Education and Science. (2017). *STEM Education Policy Statement 2017–2026*, available: <https://www.gov.ie/en/policy-information/4d40d5-stem-education-policy/#stem-education-policy-statement-2017-2026>
- English, L. D. (2016). STEM education K-12: perspectives on integration. *International Journal of STEM education*, 3(1), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-016-0036-1>
- Fitzpatrick, M., Cleary, C., & Leavy, A. (2023). *Mathifying STEM or STEMifying Math?: Challenges and possibilities for mathematics learning within integrated STEM contexts*. Manuscript submitted for publication.
- Forde, E. N., Robinson, L., Ellis, J. A., & Dare, E. A. (2023). Investigating the presence of mathematics and the levels of cognitively demanding mathematical tasks in integrated STEM units. *Disciplinary and Interdisciplinary Science Education Research*, 5(1), 3. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43031-022-00070-1>
- Honey, M., Pearson, G., & Schweingruber, H. A. (2014). *STEM Integration in K-12 Education: Status, Prospects, and an Agenda for Research*. National Academies Press.
- Hourigan, M., O'Dwyer, A., Leavy, A. M., & Corry, E. (2022). Integrated STEM – a step too far in primary education contexts? *Irish Educational Studies*, 41(4), 687-711. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03323315.2021.1899027>
- Maass, K., Geiger, V., Ariza, M. R., & Goos, M. (2019). The Role of Mathematics in interdisciplinary STEM education. *ZDM*, 51(6), 869-884. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-019-01100-5>
- Margot, K. C., & Kettler, T. (2019). Teachers' perception of STEM integration and education: a systematic literature review. *International journal of STEM education*, 6(1), 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-018-0151-2>
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment. (2023). *Primary Curriculum Framework*, available: <https://www.gov.ie/en/publication/0db24-primary-curriculum-framework/>
- Shernoff, D. J., Sinha, S., Bressler, D. M., & Ginsburg, L. (2017). Assessing teacher education and professional development needs for the implementation of integrated approaches to STEM education. *International Journal of STEM education*, 4(1), 13-13. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-017-0068-1>
- Tytler, R., Williams, G., Hobbs, L., & Anderson, J. (2019). Challenges and opportunities for a STEM interdisciplinary agenda. In B. Doig, J. Williams, D. Swanson, R. Borromeo Ferri, & P. Drake. (Eds.), *Interdisciplinary mathematics education: State of the art and beyond* (pp. 51–84). Cham, Switzerland: Springer Open.